

Assessment of Health care professionals for implementation of standard operating practices in prevention of nosocomial infection among children admitted in pediatric unit at selected hospitals of the city

Mr. Vikas Kadam,¹ Dr. (Mrs.) Jyoti V. Naikare,² Mrs. Sheetal Bardeskar,³

¹P.G. student, Sinhgad College of Nursing, Pune.

²Professor, HOD Sinhgad College of Nursing, Pune.

³Lecturer, Sinhgad College of Nursing, Pune.

Dept. of Child Health Nursing, Sinhgad College of Nursing, Pune.

Received: Apr 04, 2026

Accepted: Apr 28, 2026

Published: Apr 29, 2026

Abstract

Introduction: Nosocomial infections, also known as healthcare-associated infections (HAIs), are a major concern in pediatric units due to children's increased vulnerability caused by immature immunity, invasive procedures, and prolonged hospitalization. Effective prevention depends on strict adherence to standard operating practices (SOPs) such as hand hygiene, aseptic techniques, use of personal protective equipment, and environmental sanitation. However, variations in compliance among healthcare professionals remain a challenge.

Objectives: To assess the implementation of standard operating practices for the prevention of nosocomial infections among healthcare professionals in pediatric units, and to determine the association between practice levels and selected demographic variables.

Methodology: A quantitative, non-experimental exploratory descriptive research design was used. The study was conducted in selected hospitals of the city among 100 healthcare professionals selected through non-probability consecutive sampling. Data were collected using a demographic variables and an observational checklist based on standard operating practices. Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics, including Fisher's exact test.

Results: The findings revealed that 61% of healthcare professionals demonstrated excellent practices and 39% demonstrated good practices regarding infection prevention. None showed poor or average practices. No significant association was found between demographic variables and practice levels ($p > 0.05$).

Discussion: The study indicates a satisfactory level of adherence to infection prevention practices among healthcare professionals. However, the absence of association with demographic variables suggests that factors such as training, institutional policies, and supervision may play a more critical role in influencing compliance.

Conclusion: The study concludes that while most healthcare professionals follow appropriate infection prevention practices, continuous training, monitoring, and reinforcement of SOPs are essential to sustain high standards of care. Strengthening these practices can reduce the incidence of nosocomial infections and improve patient safety in pediatric units.

Keywords: Standard operating practices, prevention of nosocomial infection, children, health care professionals, pediatric unit.

Introduction

Children's immune systems are still developing and cannot completely create a robust defense against invasive germs, making them more susceptible to illnesses. They primarily rely on maternal antibodies and innate immunity in their early years, which progressively wane after six months, increasing their vulnerability until their adaptive immune system develops.

Nosocomial infections, also known as healthcare-associated infections (HAI), are an infection or illnesses that were not present at the time of admission but were acquired while getting medical treatment. They can manifest after discharge and happen in a variety of healthcare delivery settings, including outpatient settings, long-term care institutions, and hospitals. Occupational infections that might harm employees are also considered HAIs. When a virus or pathogens infect a vulnerable patient host, infection results. These infections are linked to indwelling medical equipment, prosthetic devices and invasive treatments and surgery in contemporary healthcare. The cause or kind of infection and the causing pathogen which might be bacterial, viral or fungal determine the etiology of HAI.

This study aims to assess the standard operating practices to the prevention of nosocomial infections among children admitted to selected pediatric units in hospitals within the city. By identifying these standard operating practices, the study hopes to provide valuable insights into the areas that need improvement and contribute to the development of strategies to reduce the incidence of nosocomial infections in pediatric care.

Background of the Study

Infection prevention plays a vital role in reducing healthcare-associated infections (HAIs), which are among the most common adverse events in healthcare worldwide. HAIs significantly increase morbidity, mortality, duration of hospital stay, and healthcare costs, especially among vulnerable populations such as neonates and children with immature immune systems and low birth weight. These infections often arise due to invasive procedures, prolonged hospitalization, and frequent contact with healthcare personnel.

Globally, millions of patients are affected by HAIs each year, with a higher burden observed in low- and middle-income countries due to limited resources, lack of standardized surveillance systems, and increasing antimicrobial resistance. Studies in India report varying infection rates, indicating inconsistencies in infection prevention practices across healthcare settings.

Effective prevention of HAIs relies on strict adherence to standard infection control measures, including hand hygiene, aseptic techniques, appropriate use of personal protective equipment, environmental sanitation, and safe biomedical waste management. A well-established infection control program, supported by trained personnel and institutional policies, is essential for ensuring compliance.

Moreover, healthcare professionals' knowledge, self-efficacy, and working conditions influence their adherence to these practices. Strengthening standard operating procedures and continuous monitoring can significantly reduce HAIs and improve patient safety in pediatric units.

Need of the Study

Aseptic technique is a fundamental component of patient care, particularly during procedures such as wound dressing, intravenous cannulation, and blood collection, where the risk of infection is high. Inadequate adherence to aseptic practices contributes significantly to healthcare-associated infections (HAIs), which remain a major cause of morbidity, mortality, prolonged hospital stay, and increased healthcare costs. Globally, HAIs account for millions of cases each year, with a substantial burden reported in India.

Nosocomial infections not only lead to physical complications but also cause psychological stress and reduced quality of life, especially among vulnerable populations such as children and immunocompromised patients. These infections are commonly transmitted through direct or indirect contact with contaminated materials, emphasizing the importance of strict infection control measures..

Therefore, this study is necessary to evaluate the implementation of standard operating practices, identify gaps in infection control, and support the development of targeted interventions to enhance patient safety and quality of care.

Methodology

A quantitative Research Approach was used to assess the Health care professionals for implementation of standard operating practices for the prevention of nosocomial infection among children. The study is carried out in selected hospitals of city. The Research Design is Non experimental Exploratory descriptive study. The samples were selected by Non-Probability consecutive sampling technique. 100 health care professionals include in this study. Data were collected by tool comparing demographic variables and Observation checklist for health care professionals. The tool was validated by experts (Content validity index -0.85) and reliability by (Cohen's kappa - 0.83). A pilot study was conducted prior to the main study assess feasibility. Data collection carried out by after obtaining prior ethical clearance and informed consent from participants. The collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics (frequency and percentage) and inferential statistics (Fisher's Exact Test) to determine the association between variables.

Results

Section A

Description of samples (Health care professionals) based on their Demographic characteristics in terms of frequency and percentage.

Table 1: Description of samples (Health care professionals) based on their Demographic characteristics in terms of frequency and percentage.

Demographic variable	Freq	%
Age		
21–30 years	49	49%
31-40 years	41	41%
41-50 years	10	10%
51-60 years	0	0%
Gender		
Male	9	9%
Female	91	91%
Education		
ANM/ GNM	35	35%
B.sc Nursing(basic)/ Post-Basic B.sc Nursing	45	45%
M.Sc. Nursing	7	7%
MBBS (MD)	13	13%
Experience		
0-5 years	32	32%
6-10 years	66	66%
11-15 years	2	2%
16-20 years	0	0%
Above 20 years	0	0%

Demographic data of health care professional includes 49% of the healthcare professionals had age 21-30 years, 41% of them had age 31-40 years and 10% of them had age 41-50 years. 9% of them were males and 91% of them were females. 35% of them were ANM/GNM, 45% of them had B.sc Nursing (basic)/ Post-Basic B.sc Nursing, 7% of them had M.Sc. nursing and 13% of them were MBBS (MD). 32% of them had 0-5 years of experience, 66% of them had 6-10 years of experience and 2% of them had 11-15 years of experience.

Section B

Analysis of data related to standard operating practices for the prevention of nosocomial infection among children admitted in pediatric unit among Health care professionals

Table 2: Standard operating practices for the prevention of nosocomial infection among children admitted in pediatric unit among Health care professionals.

Practices	Freq	%
Poor Practices (Score 0-5)	0	0%
Average Practices (Score 6-10)	0	0%
Good Practices (Score 11-15)	39	39%
Excellent Practices (Score 16-20)	61	61%

Table 2 and Fig 4 shows that 61% of them had excellent Standard operating practices for the prevention of nosocomial infection among children admitted in pediatric unit and 39% of the health care professionals had good Standard operating practices and none of them had poor Standard operating practices and average Standard operating practices for the prevention of nosocomial infection among children admitted in pediatric unit at selected hospitals of the city.

3.1: Item analysis-Hand Hygiene standard operating practices for the prevention of nosocomial infection among children admitted in pediatric unit n=100

Hand Hygiene	Freq	%
Washes hands thoroughly before and after patient contact.	70	70%
Follows all WHO-recommended steps for hand washing.	81	81%
Posters/reminders promoting hand hygiene are displayed in required areas.	100	100%
Adequate facilities (water, soap, and sanitizer) are available at required areas.	60	60%
Hospital policy emphasizes hand hygiene and mandates compliance.	100	100%

Fig 5.1 Item analysis-Hand Hygiene standard operating practices

Description: In this study 70% of the health care professional wash hands thoroughly before and after patient contact. 81% of them follow all WHO-recommended steps for hand washing. All of them had posters/reminders promoting hand hygiene is displayed in required areas. 60% of them had adequate facilities (water, soap, and sanitizer) available at required areas. All of them mentioned that their hospital policy emphasizes hand hygiene and mandates compliance.

Table 3.2: Item analysis- Use of Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) standard operating practices for the prevention of nosocomial infection among children admitted in pediatric unit. n=100

Use of Personal Protective Equipment (PPE)	Freq	%
Adequate PPE (gloves, masks, gowns, etc.) available at required points.	49	49%
Proper donning and doffing of PPE is followed as per protocol. (Researcher was not able to assess due to area limitation)	-	-
PPE is utilized appropriately as per hospital policy. (as per procedure perform in pediatric unit like specific procedure Eg. lumbar puncture)	95	95%
Proper disposal facilities and guidelines for PPE are available.	89	89%
Regular in-service education/training is conducted focusing on PPE usage	91	91%

Fig 5.2 Item analysis Use of Personal Protective Equipment

Description: 49% of the health care professional had adequate PPE (gloves, masks, gowns, etc.) available at required points. 95% of them were utilizing PPE appropriately as per hospital policy. 89% of their hospital had proper disposal facilities and guidelines for PPE. 91% of their hospital had regular in-service education/training conducted focusing on PPE usage.

Table 3.3: Item analysis- Infection Control standard operating practices for the prevention of nosocomial infection among children admitted in pediatric unit

n=100

Infection Control Practices	Freq	%
Aseptic techniques are followed according to hospital policy.	55	55%
Adequate facilities provided as per national infection control policy.	89	89%
National infection control guidelines are adhered to by healthcare staff.	100	100%
Healthcare professionals are vaccinated timely as per recommendations.	82	82%
Appropriate infection control measures and policies are made mandatory and implemented.	98	98%

Fig 5.3 Item analysis- Infection Control standard operating practices

Description: 55% of them were following Aseptic techniques according to hospital policy. 89% of them had adequate facilities provided as per national infection control policy. All of their hospital had adequate facilities provided as per national infection control policy. 82% of them were vaccinated timely as per recommendations. 98% of them had appropriate infection control measures and policies made mandatory and implemented

Table 3.4: Item analysis- Biomedical Waste (BMW) Management standard operating practices for the prevention of nosocomial infection among children admitted in pediatric unit. n=100

Biomedical Waste (BMW) Management	Freq	%
Waste disposal protocols are posted and visible in relevant areas.	100	100%
Healthcare professionals follow the correct BMW color coding system.	82	82%
Waste is disposed of correctly as per BMW guidelines.	74	74%
Waste is transported properly with appropriate labeling.	91	91%
Centralized BMW management chain is followed according to policy.	100	100%

Fig 5.4 Item analysis- Biomedical Waste (BMW) Management standard operating practices

Description: All of the health care professionals had waste disposal protocols posted and visible in relevant areas. 82% of them were following the correct BMW color coding system. 74% of them were disposing waste correctly as per BMW guidelines. 91% of them had waste transported properly with appropriate labeling. All of them were following centralized BMW management chain according to policy.

Section C**Analysis of data related to Association between Demographic variables and Practice of Health Care professionals****Table 4: Fisher's exact test for the Association between Demographic variables and Practice of Health Care professionals n=100**

Demographic variable		Practices		p-value
		Excellent	Good	
Age	21-30 years	25	24	0.214
	31-40 years	28	13	
	41-50 years	8	2	
	51-60 years	0	0	
Gender	Male	5	4	0.733
	Female	56	35	
Education	ANM/ GNM	18	17	0.397
	B.sc Nursing(basic)/ Post-Basic B.sc Nursing	29	16	
	M.Sc. Nursing	4	3	
	MBBS (MD)	10	3	
Experience	0-5 years	18	14	0.576
	6-10 years	41	25	
	11-15 years	2	0	
	16-20 years	0	0%	
	Above 20 years	0	0%	

Description: Since all p-value were large (greater than 0.05), none of the demographic variables was found to have significant association with the practices among Health Care professionals.

Discussion

The present study highlights that assess the implementation of standard operating practices for the prevention of nosocomial infection among children admitted in pediatric unit selected hospitals of the city. The finding are most (61%) of health care professionals follow the excellent standard operating practices and 39% good standard operating practices followed by for prevention of nosocomial infection. none of the demographic variables was found to have significant association with the practices among Health Care professionals.

CONCLUSION

This was Non-experimental exploratory descriptive study aim of this study to assess the standard operating practices for prevention of nosocomial infection of health care professional working in pediatric unit. The finding of the study to identify the practices of health care professional in percentage which was help to researcher. To identify the factors which was associated for the prevention of nosocomial infection? This study help to researcher to know the factors other than health staff but related to health care like hand washing, use of personal protective equipment's infection control and biomedical waste management materials.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The researcher expresses sincere gratitude to all those who contributed to the successful completion of this study. Special thanks are extended to research committee, hospital authority and health care professionals working in pediatric unit for grating permission and providing necessary support during data collection. The research is deeply thankful to the experts and guides for their valuable suggestion's guidance and encouragement throughout the study. Appreciation is also extended to the health care professionals in the study. Finally, heartfelt thanks are given to all individuals who directly or indirectly supported the completion of this research work.

REFERENCES

1. Simon, A. K., Hollander, G. A., & McMichael, A. (2015). Evolution of the immune system in humans from infancy to old age. *Proceedings of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 282(1821), 20143085. <https://royalsocietypublishing.org/rspb/article/282/1821/20143085/77935/Evolution->
2. Sikora A, Zahra F. Nosocomial infections. In: Star Pearls. Treasure Island(FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2025. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK559312/#>
3. Isma M. Assessment of Infection Control Measures and Risk Factors at Kampala International University Teaching Hospital in Bushenyi District: A Study on Staff Awareness and Implementation arch ISSN: 2705-1692 <https://doi.org/10.59298/INOSRES/2023/2.10.1000>
4. Negi S. A Study to Assess the Effectiveness of Information Booklet regarding the Knowledge and Practice of Staff Nurses to Prevent and Control Nosocomial Infection in Pediatric Unit in selected Hospitals, Dehradun, Uttarakhand. <https://d1wqtxts1xzle7.cloudfront.net/83227907/ART20192482->

5. Devi M, Asokan R, Lenka A. Effectiveness of Protocol on Standard Precautions for the Prevention of Infections in Terms of Practice among Staff Nurses working in Tertiary Care Hospital, Bhubaneswar, Odisha. *International Journal of Medical Surgical Nursing*. 2018 Apr 16; 1(1):12-20.
<https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Asokan-R/publication/346931227>
6. Allegranzi B, Bagheri S, Combescure C, Graafmans W, Attar H, Donaldson L, Pittet D. Burden of endemic health care-associated infection in developing countries: systematic review and meta analysis. *Lancet*.
[https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lancet/article/6\(10\)61458-4/](https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lancet/article/6(10)61458-4/)
7. Darmstadt GL, Saha SK, Ahmed ANU, Chowdhury MA, Law PA, Ahmed S, et al. Effect of topical treatment with skin barrier-enhancing emollients on nosocomial infections in preterm infants in Bangladesh: a randomized controlled trial. *Lancet* [Internet]. 2005; 365(9464):1039–45. Available from:
http://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S0140673605711405_12
8. Barker AK, Brown K, Siraj D, Ahsan M, Sengupta S, Safdar N. Barriers and facilitator's to infection control at a hospital in northern India: a qualitative study. *Antimicrobial Resist Infect Control* [Internet]. 2017; 6(1). Available from:
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/s13756-017-0189-9>
9. Dr. C P Baveja Textbook of Microbiology for nursing Arya Publication Company 6th edition Page No. 248
10. Akhtar S, Hussain M, Afzal M, Gilani SA. Barriers and facilitators for execution of nursing process among nurses from medical and surgical wards in a public hospital Lahore. *International Journal of Social Sciences and Management*.
<https://nepjol.info/index.php/IJSSM/article/view/2060>